

Kinetics of Formation of MgCr_2O_4 in the Solid State and its Characterisation

INDU BHUSHAN SHARMA* and SULEKHA BATRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 004

Manuscript received 10 August 1987, revised 18 January 1988, accepted 3 February 1988

Kinetics of solid state reaction between MgO and Cr_2O_3 has been investigated gravimetrically. The data follow Kroger-Ziegler equation for diffusion-controlled reactions. Elemental analysis and X-ray diffractometry indicate stoichiometry of the product as MgCr_2O_4 . Effects of doping, oxygen atmosphere and compaction on the reaction rates have been investigated. Magnetic susceptibility and electrical resistivity as functions of temperature, have been studied.

THE study of complex oxides is interesting because of the wide variety of properties they exhibit¹⁻⁴. The present study deals with kinetics of reaction between MgO and Cr_2O_3 in solid state at different temperatures, compaction pressures, oxygen atmospheres and in the presence of dopant. The data have been analysed in the light of various kinetic equations and the reaction product has been characterised by elemental analysis, X-ray diffractometry, magnetic susceptibility and electrical resistivity.

Experimental

MgO , Cr_2O_3 and LiF were of A.R. grade and used as such.

Kinetic analysis: Powdered MgO and Cr_2O_3 (200 mesh) were mixed by grinding in cyclohexane. Weighed samples of the mixed powder were heat-treated at fixed temperatures for different intervals of time in static air and withdrawn periodically for analysis. The amount of MgO reacted at any time was determined by dissolving the unreacted MgO in $2N \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, in which Cr_2O_3 and the product being insoluble. The results are plotted in Fig. 1.

The above experiments were also carried out at different pressures of oxygen in order to determine the effect of oxygen pressure. No appreciable change in α values was noticed with variation in oxygen pressure.

The mixed powders were also pressed into pellets in a hydraulic press at different pressures. The pellets were similarly subjected to heat-treatment and analysed. The results showed the enhancement of the reaction rate with increase in the compaction pressure.

MgO or Cr_2O_3 was doped with 0.1 mol % LiF , by adding aqueous solution of LiF and heating to dryness. The oxides were then mixed and heat-treated at different temperatures. From the kinetic data variation in energy of activation as a function

Fig. 1. Plots of α vs t at different temperatures.

of doping was determined. Mixed powders of MgO and Cr_2O_3 in 1:1 molar ratio were heat-treated for 72 h at 1073 K with three intermediate grindings. It was confirmed that the product did not contain unreacted MgO . A known quantity of the product was analysed for Mg and Cr by the usual methods, and the composition was found to be MgCr_2O_4 . X-Ray diffractograph of the sample (recorded on a Philips PW-1050/70 diffractometer at a scanning speed of $1^\circ/\text{min}$ 2θ value using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiations) also corroborated the findings.

Magnetic susceptibility of the sample was measured in the temperature range 385–720 K on a Gouy magnetic balance. Electrical resistivities of the sintered pellets of the product as a function of temperature were measured in static air by two-probe technique using a $4\frac{1}{2}$ digit ECIL multi-meter. The measured resistance was converted

into specific resistance from the dimensions of the pellet.

Results and Discussion

Various kinetic equations for solid state reactions, as applicable under different mechanisms, were applied to the kinetic data of the reaction. It has been observed that Kroger-Ziegler equation^{6,7} is applicable to the data. Plots of $[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/2}]^2$ vs $\ln t$ yield straight lines. The equation is based on the consideration that diffusivity of the transported species is inversely proportional to the reaction time or the rate of change of the product layer thickness is inversely proportional to the time. The energy of activation as calculated from the Arrhenius plot comes out to be 65 kJ mol^{-1} . The value is less than the generally observed values for the diffusion-controlled reactions. This suggests that diffusion through dislocations and grain boundaries also plays some part.

It has been observed from the doping study that with the doping of either MgO or Cr_2O_3 with Li^+ ion, the energy of activation decreased in both the cases. The energy of activation for the reaction is 60 and 56 kJ mol^{-1} for doping of MgO and Cr_2O_3 , respectively. The study establishes counter-cationic diffusion. The kinetic studies with different oxygen pressures suggest that diffusion of oxygen is not involved. The reaction rate is enhanced with compaction because of the increase in the reaction interface.

The magnetic studies suggest that material is paramagnetic and the plot of χ_m^{-1} vs T showed that the data follow Curie-Weiss law. From the intercept of the plot, paramagnetic Curie temperature

(θ) has been found to be -360 K . As no Neel temperature has been observed, the negative value for θ suggests that the sample is antiferromagnetic in this temperature region⁸.

Electrical resistivities (plots of $\ln \rho$ vs $1/T$) suggest that the material undergoes electronic transition around 571 K . The energy of activation for conduction before the transition in the lower temperature region is 0.608 eV , while it is 0.069 eV after the transition. The material remains semiconductor while the band gap is decreased at higher temperature. However, no such transition in the magnetic property of the material has been observed. This suggests that the nature of charge carrier remains the same.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the financial support.

References

1. J. M. LONGO in "Preparation and Characterization of Materials", eds. J. M. HONIG and C. N. R. RAO, Academic, New York, 1981, p. 29.
2. S. F. HULBERT and J. J. KLAWITTER, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1967, **50**, 484.
3. S. RAMACHANDRAN, A. BARADARAJAN and M. SATYANARAYANA, *Mat. Sci. Eng.* 1975, **20**, 68.
4. I. B. SHARMA, S. BALLA and S. BATRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985 **24**, 674.
5. "X-ray Diffraction Data Card No. 10-352", Powder Diffraction File, International Centre for Diffraction Data, Pennsylvania, 1979.
6. C. KROGER and G. ZIEGLER, *Glastech. Ber.*, 1953, **26**, 346.
7. C. KROGER and G. ZIEGLER, *Glastech. Ber.*, 1954, **27**, 199.
8. M. M. SCHIEBER, "Experimental Magnetochemistry", North-Holland Amsterdam, 1967, pp. 35, 487.